

Supplementary material: A high-resolution monitoring approach of urban CO₂ fluxes.

Part 2 - surface flux optimisation using eddy covariance observations

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Table S.1. Eddy covariance system information for the two sites in the study area.

Station acronym	Geographic location	Sensor height (m a.g.l.)	Sensor models (sonic anemometer, gas analyser)	Sonic azimuth (°)	Acquisition frequency (Hz)
BKLI	47.56173 °N, 7.58049 °E	39	HS-100 (Gill Instruments Ltd.), LI-7500 (LI-COR Inc.)	0	20
BAES	47.55123 °N, 7.59560 °E	41	CSAT3 (Campbell Scientific Inc.), LI-7500 (LI-COR Inc.)	340	20

Table S.2. Statistics on the inversion model % error reduction (ER , Eq. 6) for each flux component and the respective inversion datasets.

		Mean	Standard Deviation	Median	Percentile 5 %	Percentile 95 %
E_B	Weekday Day	47.9	28.5	57.1	3.3	83.4
	Weekday Night	59.3	29.9	74.5	5.7	86.2
	Weekend Day	49.9	26.7	63.2	6.3	78.2
	Weekend Night	56.1	32.9	72.8	3.5	87.6
E_C	Weekday Day	66.9	14.4	70.0	34.6	84.1
	Weekday Night	56.8	16.2	58.2	28.8	83.3
	Weekend Day	--	--	--	--	--
	Weekend Night	--	--	--	--	--
E_V	Weekday Day	91.3	4.0	92.1	84.9	94.4
	Weekday Night	88.4	4.9	89.5	80.0	93.7
	Weekend Day	90.5	3.2	91.3	84.2	94.0
	Weekend Night	87.0	5.8	87.8	74.2	93.0
R_H	Weekday Day	38.9	16.3	37.4	16.0	74.4
	Weekday Night	38.5	12.0	38.4	19.0	56.8
	Weekend Day	28.2	9.9	29.4	10.8	44.8
	Weekend Night	32.7	12.6	31.5	11.4	51.6
$F_{C,B}$	Weekday Day	42.6	24.5	44.5	8.0	78.6
	Weekday Night	41.4	30.7	42.7	1.2	81.8
	Weekend Day	52.9	29.4	57.7	9.6	91.3
	Weekend Night	45.0	30.8	43.6	4.6	85.2

Table S.3. Statistical metrics between eddy covariance measured $F_C (F_{C,obs})$ and source area aggregated modelled $F_C (F_{C,prior}$ and $F_{C,post})$ of the two eddy covariance sites (BKLI, BAES) for each inversion period and altogether. Units are $\mu\text{mol CO}_2 \text{ m}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$.

			<i>RMSE</i>	<i>MAE</i>	<i>Bias</i>	<i>Slope</i>	<i>Offset</i>	<i>R</i> ²
Weekday Day	BKLI	prior	6.79	5.55	-5.07	0.51	4.36	0.58
		posterior	4.77	4.14	-3.97	0.79	0.15	0.86
	BAES	prior	4.71	3.64	-2.40	0.59	8.53	0.70
		posterior	3.20	2.39	-2.11	0.90	0.57	0.89
Weekday Night	BKLI	prior	2.27	1.72	0.12	0.34	6.89	0.37
		posterior	1.86	1.51	-1.21	0.70	1.83	0.76
	BAES	prior	3.25	2.35	-0.73	0.38	6.68	0.40
		posterior	3.17	2.36	-2.32	0.56	2.93	0.78
Weekend Day	BKLI	prior	3.46	2.87	-0.67	0.49	3.92	0.70
		posterior	2.53	1.94	-1.27	0.69	1.55	0.81
	BAES	prior	4.80	3.91	2.25	0.40	10.48	0.24
		posterior	2.45	1.76	-1.00	0.65	3.71	0.78
Weekend Night	BKLI	prior	2.06	1.51	0.10	0.41	5.21	0.39
		posterior	1.56	1.15	-0.86	0.72	1.54	0.76
	BAES	prior	2.97	2.04	-0.74	0.34	5.44	0.34
		posterior	2.76	2.11	-1.78	0.55	2.39	0.66
ALL	prior	4.24	3.07	-1.26	0.69	3.39	0.76	
	posterior	3.10	2.31	-2.01	0.86	0.04	0.92	